

On the Synthesis of Some Chlorinated Isocoumarins

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The dihydroisocoumarin(V) and the isochroman(XII) have been synthesised during experiments on the synthesis of some natural chlorinated isocoumarins.

THREE dihydroisocoumarins, 3-methyl-6-methoxy-8-hydroxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin(I)¹⁻³, 5,7-dichloro-3-methyl-6-methoxy-8-hydroxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin(II) and 7-chloro-3-methyl-6-methoxy-8-hydroxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin(III) were isolated from *Sporomia* fungus by McGahren and Mitscher⁴. The present communication deals with experiments towards the syntheses of these natural products. The homophthalic acid⁵(VII) was

- (I) $R=R_1=R_2=H$
 (II) $R=H, R_1=R_2=Cl$
 (III) $R=R_2=H, R_1=Cl$
 (IV) $R=R_1=H, R_2=Cl$
 (V) $R=CH_3, R_1=H, R_2=Cl$
 (VI) $R=CH_3, R_1=R_2=H$

- (VII) $R_1=R_2=CH_3, R_3=H$
 (VIII) $R_1=R_2=CH_3, R_3=H$
 (IX) $R_1=R_2=CH_3, R_3=Cl$
 (X) $R_1=OH, R_2=H, R_3=Cl$

esterified with diazomethane to give (VIII) which on chlorination with excess (3 mole) of sulphuryl chloride in presence of catalytic amount of benzoyl peroxide⁵ afforded a monochloro derivative. This was assigned the structure (IX) following McGahren *et al*⁴ who showed that chlorination of (-) 6,8-dimethoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin(VI) with sulphuryl chloride in presence of aluminium chloride afforded 5-chloro-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin(V). The diester(IX) was converted into the half-ester(X) by partial hydrolysis with methanolic potassium hydroxide. The acid chloride of (X) on treatment with diethyl ethoxymagnesiummalonate followed by subsequent hydrolysis afforded a mixture of 5-chloro-6-methoxy-8-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (arising by demethylation) and its *o*-methyl ether. The former was methylated with methyl iodide and potassium carbonate (anhydrous) in acetone to give the latter which on hydrogenation in presence of palladised charcoal afforded the (\pm) dihydroisocoumarin(V).

In experiments on a new synthesis of (I), 3,5-dimethoxy-phenylacetic acid⁶ was converted into 3,5-dimethoxybenzyl methyl ketone which was reduced to the corresponding alcohol with potassium borohydride. Chloromethylation of this alcohol with formaldehyde and hydrochloric acid

gave 6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman(XI) in a very poor yield presumably due to phenol-formal-

- (XI) $R=H$ (XIII) $R=OH_2$
 (XII) $R=OH_2Cl$ (XIV) $R=OHO$

dehyde type of polymerisation. But chloromethylation with monochloromethyl methyl ether in presence of fused zinc chloride yielded the same isochroman(XI) together with another compound, m.p. 235° (M^+ , $m/e=428$) which is undoubtedly di-(6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochromanyl)methane (RCH_2R ; $R=6,8$ -dimethoxy-3-methylisochromanyl). This is confirmed by the presence of ion peaks at m/e 428 (M^+); 353, 221 (RCH_2^+), 207 (R^+), 191 (RCH_2^+-HCHO), 177 (R^+-HCHO) and 147 in its mass spectrum.

When the amount of monochloromethyl methyl ether and $ZnCl_2$ was varied in the reaction a different compound analysing for $C_{15}H_{17}O_3Cl$ was obtained to which the structure (XII) may be attributed. The point of entry of the chloromethyl group at 5-position is based on the following premises: (i) pmr spectrum of (XII) showed a single aromatic proton at τ 3.6. The high field absorption indicates the flanking of two shielding⁷ methoxy groups (ii) chlorination⁴ of (VI) affords the related 5-chloro derivative but not the 7-chloro isomer.

The chloromethylisochroman(XII) on reduction with hydrogen in presence of palladised charcoal afforded (XIII) whose pmr spectrum showed a doublet at τ 8.62 (3H, $J=6.5$ Hz; CH_2CH_3), a multiplet at τ 7.4-7.65 (1H, CH_2CHCH_3), a singlet at τ 6.6 (3H, $Ar-CH_3$), a singlet at τ 6.12 (3H, OCH_3), a singlet at τ 6.1 (3H, OCH_3), a singlet at τ 5.45 (2H, $Ar-CH_2-O-$), a doublet at τ 5.2 (2H, $J=9.5$ Hz; $Ar-CH_2CH-$) and a singlet at τ 3.55 (1H, aromatic at C-7). Sommelet reaction of (XII) with hexamethylenetetramine yielded 5-aldehyde-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman(XIV) characterised as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. Experiments on the oxidation of (XI) with either SeO_2 or CrO_3 to the dihydroisocoumarin(VI) have been unsuccessful so far.

Experimental

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer, model 237.

Dimethyl 6-chloro-3,5-dimethoxyhomophthalate: 3,5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid⁸ was esterified with diazomethane in the usual manner to give dimethyl 3,5-dimethoxyhomophthalate as an oil which was distilled at 160°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 58.1; H, 6.0. Calculated for C₁₈H₁₆O₆: C, 58.2; H, 6.0%).

Dimethyl 3,5-dimethoxyhomophthalate (1.0 g) in dry carbon tetrachloride (60 ml) was treated with sulphuryl chloride (0.765 g) in dry carbon tetrachloride (20 ml) and a few crystals of benzoyl peroxide at 0°. The mixture was kept in a refrigerator for 72 hrs. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure when a thick oil was obtained. This was chromatographed over alumina using benzene as eluent to give dimethyl 6-chloro-3,5-dimethoxyhomophthalate (0.8 g) which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless crystals, m.p. 108°. (Found: C, 51.4; H, 5.0. C₁₈H₁₅O₆Cl requires C, 51.5; H, 4.9%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1755 cm⁻¹ (aliphatic ester carbonyl) and 1725 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ester carbonyl).

2-Methoxycarbonyl-6-chloro-3,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid: The above ester (0.8 g) was refluxed with methanolic potassium hydroxide (1.5 ml, 10%) for 25 minutes. After removal of methanol, the solution was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether to remove any unchanged diester. The aqueous layer was acidified with hydrochloric acid to give 2-methoxycarbonyl-6-chloro-3,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid which was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles (0.5 g), m.p. 203°. (Found: C, 49.8; H, 4.8. C₁₈H₁₅O₆Cl requires C, 50.0; H, 4.5%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1726 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ester carbonyl) and 1700 cm⁻¹ (carboxyl).

5-Chloro-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin: A mixture of 2-methoxycarbonyl-6-chloro-3,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid (0.5 g), dry benzene (15 ml), thionyl chloride (1 ml) and a drop of dry pyridine was refluxed on water bath for 2 hrs. The benzene and excess of thionyl chloride were removed under reduced pressure and last traces of thionyl chloride were removed by three successive additions of dry benzene followed by its removal under reduced pressure. The resultant acid chloride was obtained as thick oil.

Diethyl ethoxymagnesiummalonate was then prepared by heating, with exclusion of moisture, a mixture of clean magnesium (170 mg), dry ethanol (0.16 ml) and carbon tetrachloride (1 drop) and then adding, after the reaction had started, a mixture of dry ethanol (0.6 ml), diethyl malonate (1 ml) and dry ether (10 ml). The mixture was gently refluxed for 3 hrs when nearly all the magnesium dissolved. An ethereal solution of the acid chloride prepared above was added to this mixture and refluxed gently for 2 hrs when the magnesium complex separated as jelly. The reaction mixture was decomposed with dilute sul-

phuric acid and extracted with ether. After removal of ether an oil was obtained which was refluxed with a mixture of acetic acid (5 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 ml) for 4 hrs. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water respectively and dried (MgSO₄). On evaporation of the solvent a thick oily mass was obtained. This was triturated with benzene to give 5-chloro-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin which was recrystallised from benzene in colourless needles (50 mg), m.p. 154°. (Found: C, 56.4; H, 4.6. C₁₈H₁₅O₄Cl requires C, 56.6; H, 4.3%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1740 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl) and 1724 cm⁻¹.

On removal of benzene from the mother liquor a thick oil was obtained which was believed to contain 5-chloro-6-methoxy-8-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin. This was methylated by refluxing its solution in acetone (10 ml) with methyl iodide (4 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g) for 20 hrs. On working up in the usual manner 5-chloro-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (150 mg) was obtained which was crystallised from benzene as colourless needles, m.p. 154°.

5-Chloro-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin: 5-Chloro-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (150 mg) in ethanol (10 ml) was hydrogenated in presence of palladised charcoal (50 mg; 10%) till no more hydrogen was consumed. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to give 5-chloro-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (20 mg) as oil which could not be solidified [lit.¹, m.p. 119-120° for (-) enantiomer]. (Found: C, 55.9; H, 5.4. C₁₈H₁₅O₄Cl requires C, 56.2; H, 5.1%); ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 1720 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl).

3,5-Dimethoxybenzyl methyl ketone: A solution of 3,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid⁹ (0.6 g) in dry benzene (10 ml) was treated with oxalyl chloride (0.6 ml) at 10° for one hour and left overnight at room temperature. Next day, it was worked up as usual to give the related acid chloride as light brown oil. A solution of this acid chloride in ether (15 ml) was added with stirring to an ethereal solution of diethyl ethoxymagnesiummalonate prepared from magnesium (140 mg) as described earlier. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs when the magnesium complex separated as jelly. The mixture was cooled, decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether. Removal of ether gave an oil which was refluxed with a mixture of acetic acid (1.2 ml), sulphuric acid (0.12 ml) and water (0.7 ml) for 5 hrs. After removal of solvent under reduced pressure, the mixture was basified and extracted with ether, the extract washed with water and dried (MgSO₄). Removal of ether gave 3,5-dimethoxybenzyl methyl ketone (0.4 g), b.p. 128°/1.5 mm. (Found: C, 67.9; H, 7.4. C₁₁H₁₄O₃ requires C, 68.0; H, 7.2%); ν_{\max} (neat) 1720 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative was prepared and crystallised from acetic

acid in needles, m.p. 145°. (Found: N, 14.6. $C_{17}H_{18}O_6N_4$ requires N, 14.9%).

1-(3',5'-Dimethoxyphenyl)propan-2-ol: A solution of potassium borohydride (0.4 g) in water (10 ml) containing a drop of concentrated sodium hydroxide solution was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of 3,5-dimethoxybenzyl methyl ketone (2.8 g) in methanol (20 ml) at 25° during one hr. The mixture was left overnight at room temperature. Next day, the mixture was acidified with sulphuric acid to destroy excess potassium borohydride and was extracted with ether repeatedly. The combined ethereal extract was washed with sodium bisulphite solution and saturated sodium chloride solution respectively and then dried ($MgSO_4$). Removal of ether afforded 1-(3',5'-dimethoxyphenyl)-propan-2-ol (2.3 g), b. p. 168°/0.8 mm. (Found: C, 67.1; H, 8.6. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.3; H, 8.2%); ν_{max} (neat) 3420 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl).

6,8-Dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman: Dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed into a mixture of 1-(3',5'-dimethoxyphenyl)propan-2-ol (4 g) and aqueous formaldehyde (8 ml; 37%) with stirring for 3 hrs. Heat evolved as the reaction proceeded and the temperature was maintained at 20° by external cooling. The mixture diluted with water and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water respectively and finally dried ($MgSO_4$). The thick oil obtained on removal of ether was distilled at 175-80°/0.5 mm to give 6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman (0.5 g) as solid which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles, m.p. 96°. (Found: C, 69.0; H, 7.4. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1602 cm^{-1} .

Di-(6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman-5-yl)-methane: Anhydrous zinc chloride (250 mg) was added to a solution of 1-(3',5'-dimethoxyphenyl)propan-2-ol (0.5 g) in monochloromethyl methyl ether (15 ml) and shaken at 18° for one minute. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with water and dried ($CaCl_2$). After removal of solvent the residual mass was triturated with ether when di-(6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman-5-yl)-methane (0.2 g) was obtained as solid. This was crystallised from acetic acid in shining colourless needles, m.p. 235°, M^+ , $m/e=428$. (Found: C, 70.1; H, 7.6. $C_{25}H_{32}O_6$ requires C, 70.4; H, 7.5%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1601 cm^{-1} .

The ethereal mother liquor on evaporation gave an oil which was distilled at 170-80°/0.5 mm to give 6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman (0.1 g),

m. p. 95° identical with the previous sample prepared by a different method.

5-Chloromethyl-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman: In a similar experiment 1-(3',5'-dimethoxyphenyl)propan-2-ol (0.5 g) in chloromethyl methyl ether (20 ml) was treated with fused zinc chloride (150 mg) at 18° for one minute. The reaction mixture was worked up in the above manner to give 5-chloromethyl-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman (0.3 g) which was crystallised from petroleum ether in colourless prisms, m.p. 128-29°. (Found: C, 60.7; H, 7.0; $C_{18}H_{17}O_3Cl$ requires C, 60.8; H, 6.6%).

5-Methyl-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman: The foregoing isochroman (0.2 g) in methanol (10 ml) was hydrogenated in presence of palladised charcoal (0.1 g; 30%) till no more hydrogen was consumed. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual to give 5-methyl-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman (170 mg) which was crystallised from petroleum ether in colourless needles, m.p. 70°. (Found: C, 69.9; H, 7.9. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 70.3; H, 8.1%).

5-Formyl-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman: A mixture of 5-chloromethyl-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylisochroman (0.3 g) in acetic acid (2 ml), water (2 ml) and hexamethylenetetramine (280 mg) was refluxed for 10 hrs. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.6 ml) was added and again refluxed for an additional hour. After cooling, the mixture was extracted with ether, the extract washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and water respectively and finally dried ($MgSO_4$). Removal of solvent afforded the aldehyde (XIV) which was characterised by the preparation of its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative crystallising from acetic acid in red needles, m. p. 275°. (Found: C, 54.5; H, 5.0; N, 13.3. $C_{19}H_{20}O_7N_4$ requires C, 54.8; H, 4.8; N, 13.5%).

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